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Evaluation of Purolite® A110 and Lewatit® VP OC 1065 in a 1kg_{CO2}/day fixed bed DAC unit.

A. Srinivas^a, D.W.F. Brilman^{a*}

^aUniversity of Twente, Drienerloaan 5, Enschede, 7522NB, The Netherlands.

Abstract

Direct Air Capture (DAC) plays a key role in achieving net-zero carbon emissions. Solid amine sorbent-based adsorption is one of the most promising DAC technologies. Testing sorbents and processes under real-life conditions is critical for evaluating performance and gaining insights for improvement. These insights are essential for further development and scaling up DAC efforts. In this work, two commercially available amine-based sorbents, Purolite® A110 and Lewatit® VP OC 1065, were tested in a 1 kg_{CO2}/day fixed-bed DAC pilot plant. This study examines the effects of weather conditions and operational parameters such as cycle time on CO₂ working capacity, CO₂ productivity, and energy duty. The loss of sorbent activity during the test campaigns is also examined.

Keywords: Direct Air Capture; Solid amine Sorbent; Pilot Plant; Purolite; Lewatit; Operation; CCU.

1. Introduction

The significance of Direct air capture (DAC) lies in its ability to offer a sustainable source of carbon, derived directly from the atmosphere, which can be harnessed as a raw material for various applications like microalgae production, production of methanol and e-fuels which utilizes CO₂ [1]. Among different direct air capture technologies, solid amine based adsorbents are undergoing rapid development. Solid amine based adsorbents are preferred in some cases because of their high CO₂ adsorption capacity in direct air capture conditions and ability to use low grade heat of temperatures 90-120°C for desorption of captured CO₂ and water.

Different types of adsorbents have been studied for application in lab-scale, pilot, and large-scale DAC units. Previous investigations at the University of Twente (UT) have demonstrated that Lewatit® VP OC 1065, manufactured by Lanxess, a commercial amine-based sorbent, has the potential to serve as a standard for direct air capture. It has been utilized in earlier test campaigns of the fixed bed, which is one of the main focuses of this study, as well as the 10kg/day_{CO2} circulating bed DAC pilot currently operational at UT [2, 3]. However, recent studies have highlighted the potential of Purolite® A110 (Purolite), a product of Ecolab, another commercial amine-based adsorbent under direct air capture conditions [4]. In this investigation, the applicability and performance of two commercially available amine-based sorbents, Purolite® A110 and Lewatit® VP OC 1065, for fixed-bed direct air capture is assessed.

The organization of the manuscript is as follows: In section 2, the process and need for sorbent development is discussed in detail along with the comparison of properties of Lewatit and Purolite. In section 3, the results of the

initial tests is discussed in detail and in Section 4, The effect of cycle time on the system performance is discussed. In Section 5, the effect of relative humidity is presented. In section 6, the overall sorbent performance is analyzed and finally, the discussion and outlook are presented in Section 7.

2. Process description and Research motivation

2.1. Process description

The $1\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{day}$ fixed bed DAC pilot developed at the University of Twente employs a steam-assisted temperature vacuum swing adsorption process, the pilot comprises four fixed bed reactors operating in parallel. At any given time, three beds are in adsorption mode, while one will be in regeneration mode. Concentrated CO_2 released during regeneration is subsequently compressed and stored in a buffer vessel. CO_2 is captured from the air during the adsorption process, utilizing the commercially available amine based sorbents, Purolite A110 in the first bed and Lewatit VP OC 1065 in the rest. This process takes place within a fixed-bed reactor, where heating/cooling fluid circulates through heat exchange coils inside the reactor. As the adsorption progresses, CO_2 along with water, adsorb to the amine groups within the adsorbent until saturation is reached, indicating the need for regeneration of the reactor. The schematic of a reactor system is shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Schematic representation of the reactor arrangement in $1\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{day}$ DAC pilot.

The process of releasing the captured CO_2 from the adsorbent is known as regeneration, conducted under vacuum and elevated temperatures with steam purging. Regeneration happens in four steps: (1) Vacuumization, (2) Heating, (3) Desorption, and (4) Cooling.

Given the property of the adsorbent to undergo rapid degradation under high oxygen partial pressures and elevated temperatures, it is important to minimize the oxygen partial pressure before heating the sorbent. Thus, the reactor is evacuated to pressures around 40-50 mbara at the beginning of the regeneration process. This is the vacuumization

step (1). Subsequently, the sorbent is heated to temperatures around 90°C. Heating the reactor and adsorbent prior to desorption is essential to avoid steam condensation within the reactor and on the adsorbent surface. Reactor heating is achieved by circulating hot water through the heat exchange coils within the reactor. This is the heating step (2).

Once the reactor reaches the required temperature, steam is introduced into the system, this marks the beginning of the desorption phase (3). After desorption is complete, the sorbent must be cooled to below 40°C before it is exposed to air for adsorption, minimizing the risk of sorbent degradation. This is the cooling phase (4). Cooling is facilitated by circulating cooling water through the heat exchange tubes within the reactor. The conclusion of the cooling phase signals the end of the regeneration process, making the reactor available for adsorption. Vacuum is established during the regeneration process using a vacuum pump. The gases released during regeneration are subsequently compressed and stored in a 100-liter storage vessel using a gas compressor.

2.2. Need for sorbent development

A great deal of research is being conducted on adsorbents for direct air capture due to the critical need to efficiently capture CO₂ from the atmosphere. Studying different adsorbents is essential because each material has unique properties that impact its effectiveness in real-world applications. Key characteristics include, but are not limited to, high CO₂ equilibrium capacity, which ensures that the adsorbent can store a significant amount of CO₂ per unit mass, and fast capture kinetics, which allow for quicker CO₂ uptake. Minimizing water co-adsorption is also crucial, as excess water can reduce the performance and energy efficiency of the capture process. Additionally, minimizing the degradation of the sorbent is important to reduce long-term costs. These factors help identify sorbents that can operate efficiently under varying environmental conditions, making the process more energy-efficient economically viable.

One of the main KPIs for DAC is energy efficiency. To determine the theoretical effect of sorbent performance on the energy efficiency of a 1 kg_{CO2}/day fixed-bed DAC pilot, a sensitivity analysis under constant weather conditions and sorbent properties, presented in Figure 2, was performed by varying the CO₂ working capacity (mol_{CO2}/kg_s) and water working capacity (mol_{H2O}/kg_s) to study their effect on energy duty (MJ/kg_{CO2}). The operational parameters that influence the energy duty for the 1 kg_{CO2}/day fixed-bed DAC were calculated based on correlations presented by Schellevis et al. [2].

(a) Contour plot for effect on energy duty

(b) Effect of CO₂ working capacity on Energy duty

Fig 2. Effect of CO₂ and H₂O working capacity on Energy duty of the DAC unit.

From Figure 2(a) and (b), it is evident that the highest CO₂ working capacity and lowest water working capacity result in the lowest energy duty. The reduction in energy duty is significant up to CO₂ working capacities of 1 mol/kg, after which it slows down. An increase in water working capacity leads to higher energy duty for the system. Although

higher water working capacity comes with an energy penalty, it may be beneficial in some cases, as water co-adsorption on amine-based sorbents can enhance CO₂ adsorption [5, 6].

Apart from energy duty, sorbent costs play a crucial role in the overall economics of the DAC process. Previous analysis for the 1kg_{CO2}/day fixed-bed DAC unit, shows that sorbent costs represent a significant portion of the total cost of capture, assuming a sorbent cost of €30/kg and a lifetime of 2 years, the analysis indicates that for most data points analyzed, sorbent costs contribute 20-30% of the total capture costs, which is considerable [7]. Considering these factors, there is a strong need for the development of sorbents that offer better capture performance, are more cost-effective, and exhibit greater stability against degradation.

2.3. Sorbent property comparison

Several sorbents have been developed and studied for application in DAC. This study focuses on two commercially available, solid amine-based sorbents: Purolite® A110 and Lewatit® VP OC 1065. Both the sorbents are microporous, divinylbenzene crosslinked polystyrene spherical particles with primary amine as functional group. Detailed studies previously conducted by the SPT group at the University of Twente examined the physical and adsorption properties of Lewatit® VP OC 1065, including, but not limited to, measurements of CO₂ and H₂O adsorption and co-adsorption isotherms and kinetics [6, 8], thermal conductivity [8], sorbent bed properties [9], and degradation [10]. A recent study comparing the physical and adsorption properties of Purolite® A110 and Lewatit® VP OC 1065 [4] concluded that Purolite® has a lower bed and particle density, higher bed volume, and greater CO₂ and water adsorption capacity, while the other measured properties are similar to those of Lewatit® VP OC 1065.

To compare the performance of the two sorbents, the CO₂ equilibrium capacity and CO₂ uptake rates were measured using a Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter Thermogravimetric Analyzer at 40°C and various CO₂ partial pressures. The TGA results are presented in Figure 3(a) and (b).

Fig 3. CO₂ equilibrium capacity (a) and uptake rate (b) measured in TGA at 40°C.

As seen in Figure 3(a), Purolite shows a higher CO₂ uptake capacity than Lewatit at all CO₂ partial pressures. At CO₂ partial pressures above 0.1 bar, Purolite's capacity is 30% higher than that of Lewatit, and at CO₂ partial pressures below 0.1 bar, Purolite demonstrates approximately 40% higher capacity. This advantage indicates that Purolite may perform much better in the direct air capture region. While the CO₂ uptake rate is not quantified in this study, Figure 3(b) indicates that at a CO₂ partial pressure of 0.15 bar and 40°C, the CO₂ uptake rate of Purolite is similar to that of Lewatit. Further studies are needed to properly quantify the adsorption kinetics of Purolite.

3. Results of Initial test campaign

To test the sorbents in the 1 kg_{CO2}/day pilot, the first reactor was filled with Purolite, while the remaining reactors were filled with Lewatit. To measure the CO₂ breakthrough curves accurately, additional LI-840A analyzers were installed alongside the integrated MH-Z16 sensors. To provide additional cooling, the cooling water was circulated through a Julabo F25 cooling water bath as an alternative to an air-cooled radiator water cooler. The primary aim of the initial test campaign was to evaluate the performance of the two adsorbents during long-term operation of the unit under nearly constant weather conditions.

3.1. Weather conditions

Weather conditions, particularly temperature and humidity, greatly influence DAC unit performance and energy duty. For amine-based adsorbents, higher humidity enhances CO₂ capture capacity [5, 6, 11] but also increases the desorption energy, requiring a balance between maximizing capture and minimizing energy costs. The tests were conducted indoors at the High Pressure Lab at the University of Twente, where weather conditions remained nearly constant. Ambient conditions, including temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ concentration during the initial test campaign, are shown in Figure 4.

Fig.4. Variation of air inlet temperature (a), relative humidity (b) and CO₂ concentration (c) with cycle number.

Since the test campaigns were conducted indoors, the ambient temperature remained constant at $25.5 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, as shown in Figure 4a. However, relative humidity varied from 40% to 65% (Figure 4b), as it was not controlled by the atmosphere controller of the High Pressure Lab. The variation of ambient CO_2 concentration is shown in Figure 4c. Initially, pressurized CO_2 was vented into the surroundings of the DAC unit, which increased the average ambient CO_2 concentration. In the second half of the campaign, the pressurized CO_2 vent was redirected to the ventilation system, normalizing the average ambient CO_2 content. In addition to weather conditions, the beds were cooled using a water bath during the first half of the campaign and a radiator during the second half.

3.2. CO_2 breakthrough curves

The CO_2 breakthrough curves are used to qualitatively assess the degree of desorption and the extent of sorbent saturation at the end of the adsorption phase. They also facilitate the calculation of the working capacity for each sorbent. Most cycles from this test campaign were reproducible, as demonstrated in Figure A.1.1 in Appendix A.1, which illustrates the reproducibility of the CO_2 breakthrough curves and vacuum pressure during desorption.

Fig.5. CO_2 breakthrough curves for Reactor 1 (Purolite) and Reactor 2 (Lewatit).

From the breakthrough curves presented in Figure 5, it is evident that, at the end of the adsorption phase within the selected cycle time, Lewatit is nearly saturated with CO_2 , while Purolite is much further away from saturation. The slight increase in CO_2 concentration during the cycle corresponds to the cooling cycle of the other reactors (the dotted vertical lines in Figure 5 indicates the end of this cooling phase).

This increase is attributed to the cooling water circuit's inability to dissipate enough heat, which causes the reactors currently adsorbing to heat up. This phenomenon is well documented by Schellevis et al. [2]. Given that the breakthrough curve of Purolite is much further from saturation in this case of cycle time, it would be worthwhile to study the effect of different cycle time on system performance.

3.3. Productivity and Energy Duty

The CO_2 working capacity, CO_2 productivity, and energy duty of the unit are the most important operating KPIs for the DAC system, allowing for a comparison of the performance of both sorbents. Figure 6a and 6b illustrates the variation in CO_2 working capacity and productivity throughout the test campaign. As shown in the figure, the average working capacity and productivity for Purolite is 20% higher than that of Lewatit. The variation in working capacity during the first half of the campaign is primarily due to variation in relative humidity and the local venting of CO_2 , as mentioned in Section 3.1; this variation decreases once the vent is redirected outside of the High Pressure Lab.

Fig 6. Variation of CO₂ working capacity and productivity of Purolite (a) and Lewatit (b) with cycle number.

The sudden drop in working capacity at the beginning of the second half of the campaign results from the combined effects of lower ambient CO₂ concentration and higher average bed temperature after cooling (Figure A.1.2 in Appendix A.1), which occurred due to the use of an air cooled radiator to cool the cooling water.

Understanding the energy duty distribution is crucial for optimizing the performance of the DAC unit. By identifying the primary energy consumers, targeted improvements can be made to reduce overall energy requirements and enhance efficiency. Investigations in the upcoming sections will focus on adjusting system parameters, such as cycle time etc. to evaluate their impact on the energy consumption and CO₂ capture capabilities of both sorbents. This optimization could lead to more energy-efficient and cost-effective solutions.

Fig 7. Comparison of energy duty of the unit for Purolite and Lewatit.

The distribution of overall energy duty among individual consumers, as well as the comparison of energy duty for Purolite and Lewatit, is presented in Figure 7. For this analysis, one cycle from the second half of the test campaign was selected. As shown in the figure, the overall energy duty (MJ/kgCO₂) for Purolite is approximately 25% lower than that for Lewatit. The major energy consumers are the sensible heat of the reactor and the heat required for purge gas, which together account for about 40% of the total energy duty. This serves as an initial assessment of both sorbents, noting that the operation of the unit in this campaign has not been optimized in favor of either sorbent.

4. Effect of cycle time

The adsorption-regeneration cycle time is a critical parameter for efficient operation of the unit. A shorter cycle time allows for more adsorption-regeneration cycles per day, leading to more frequent temperature and pressure swings in the reactor system, which can increase the overall energy duty. Conversely, a longer cycle time reduces the number of swings, potentially lowering energy requirements. However, the effect of cycle time on CO₂ working capacity and productivity is less straightforward and varies depending on the type of sorbent used in the system.

Fig 8. Cycle time distribution for different cycle lengths

This study adopts the cycle times suggested by Schellevis et al. [2], using three different levels: long, medium, and short cycle times. The time distribution for various sub-processes at each cycle time is shown in Figure 8 and detailed in Table A.2.1 in Appendix A.2. The experimental campaign lasted several days to ensure data reproducibility.

4.1. CO₂ breakthrough curves

To assess the extent of desorption, degree of saturation, and CO₂ working capacity of each sorbent, the CO₂ breakthrough curves for different cycle times are presented for Purolite and Lewatit in Figures 9a and 9b, respectively.

(a) CO₂ breakthrough curves for Purolite (R1). (b) CO₂ breakthrough curves for Lewatit (R2).

Fig 9. CO₂ breakthrough curves for different cycle times for Purolite (a) and Lewatit (b).

As shown in Figures 9a and 9b, the initial drop in CO₂ concentration at the reactor outlet is less for both Purolite and Lewatit at shorter cycle times compared to medium and long cycle times. This suggests that the extent of sorbent desorption is low and insufficient in shorter cycles, while longer cycle times promote more desorption, benefiting the process.

Comparing the reactor outlet CO₂ concentration at the end of adsorption for Purolite and Lewatit, it is evident that for all cycle times, Lewatit bed's outlet CO₂ concentration nearly reaches the inlet level, indicating the sorbent bed is almost fully saturated with CO₂.

In contrast, for Purolite, the outlet CO₂ concentration remains below the inlet level, suggesting the bed is far from saturation at the end of adsorption and has potential for further CO₂ adsorption if the adsorption time is increased or if the air inlet velocity is increased. Thus, Purolite experiences a greater impact from increased cycle time due to its lower saturation level at the end of adsorption.

4.2. Productivity and Energy Duty

Figures 10a and 10b show the CO₂ working capacity and CO₂ productivity for Purolite and Lewatit, respectively. Increasing cycle time raises the CO₂ working capacity of both sorbents, with a more pronounced effect for Purolite than for Lewatit. For Purolite, the CO₂ working capacity increases by approximately 55% from short to long cycle times, while for Lewatit, this increase is around 35%. In contrast, CO₂ productivity for Lewatit decreases by 20% with longer cycle times, while it remains nearly constant for Purolite.

Fig 10. Variation of CO₂ working capacity (a) and CO₂ productivity (b) with cycle time.

The increase in CO₂ working capacity within each cycle, especially for medium and long cycle times, is attributed to the rise in relative humidity of the inlet air. Figure A.2.2 in Appendix A.2 provides a plot of CO₂ working capacity of Purolite and Lewatit alongside relative humidity across cycle times, illustrating the variation of relative humidity over time. The effect of relative humidity on adsorption capacity of sorbents and enhancement of CO₂ adsorption is discussed in the next section.

Figure 11a shows the energy duty distribution for both sorbents across different cycle times. As noted previously, Purolite consistently has a lower energy duty than Lewatit in all cases. With increasing cycle time, Purolite's energy duty decreases by 20%, compared to only a 5% decrease for Lewatit. The reactor's sensible heat, the largest energy consumer, also decreases with longer cycle times - by approximately 44% for Purolite and 35% for Lewatit.

Fig 11. Comparison of energy duty of the unit for Purolite and Lewatit for different cycle times.

This analysis leads to different conclusions for each sorbent. For Lewatit, short or long cycle time do not yield favorable results; the medium cycle time appears to be the most advantageous in terms of both CO₂ productivity and energy duty. In contrast, for Purolite, longer cycle times prove to be more beneficial.

5. Effect of relative humidity

As discussed in previous sections, the relative humidity of the inlet air has a substantial impact on system performance. When operating the unit outdoors, temperature and relative humidity fluctuate both seasonally and throughout the day. This variability makes it essential to understand the impact of relative humidity on CO₂ working capacity and the associated energy penalty for water desorption.

This section examines how variations in relative humidity influence unit performance. Since relative humidity was not a controlled variable during testing, data points with significant fluctuations in humidity when operating conditions were constant were selected to analyze its effect on system performance. The variation of CO₂ working capacity for Purolite and Lewatit with relative humidity is presented in Figure 12.

Fig 12. Effect of relative humidity on CO₂ working capacity of Purolite and Lewatit.

Figure 12 presents three instances during the campaign where operating conditions, such as air velocity, purge rate and desorption temperature remained constant while the relative humidity of the inlet air varied. An increase in relative humidity led to a higher CO₂ working capacity for both sorbents, consistent with findings in the literature [5, 6, 11]. The selected data points indicate a 10-20% enhancement in CO₂ working capacity due to increased humidity. A similar increase in relative humidity results in approximately a 15% increase in CO₂ equilibrium capacity for Lewatit under direct air capture conditions [11], though comparable data for Purolite is currently unavailable.

Fig 13. Enhancement of CO₂ working capacity of Purolite and Lewatit with relative humidity.

Figure 13 compares the increase in CO₂ working capacity for Lewatit and Purolite as relative humidity varies. A linear fit indicates that CO₂ working capacity improves by about 17% for Purolite and 10% for Lewatit with increased humidity. This initial analysis highlights a notable impact of relative humidity on CO₂ working capacity for both sorbents, with Purolite showing a greater enhancement than Lewatit. This will have different implications on system performance optimization for different sorbents in different weather conditions which has to be studied in detail.

6. Sorbent performance

Amine-based sorbents are prone to oxidative degradation at elevated temperatures [10]. Due to the modular design of the DAC unit, achieving perfect vacuum sealing in the reactors is challenging. Consequently, during desorption, when reactors are under high temperature and vacuum, the sorbent is exposed to oxygen, accelerating degradation.

Fig 14. Comparison of CO₂ capacity of Fresh and used Purolite (a) and Lewatit (a) measured with TGA at 40°C.

Figure 14a and 14b show the CO₂ equilibrium capacity of Purolite and Lewatit, measured by TGA at various CO₂ partial pressures before and after the experimental campaigns. Purolite exhibits a 17-20% loss in capacity, while Lewatit shows a 20-30% loss across different CO₂ partial pressures. Notably, the capacity loss is greater at lower CO₂ partial pressures compared to higher CO₂ partial pressures. This may be attributed to the degradation of more active adsorption sites, which are essential for CO₂ uptake at low CO₂ partial pressures, while the less active sites remain relatively unaffected. However, further analysis is needed to confirm this hypothesis.

Fig 15. CO₂ working capacity trend over the duration of the test campaigns.

The observed decrease in working capacity for both sorbents, shown later in Figure 15, indicates an average loss of around 55% after approximately 2000 hours of operation. This significant degradation emphasizes the need for further investigation to enhance sorbent durability. Such degradation affects not only CO₂ capture efficiency but also energy consumption, as lower sorbent capacity necessitates more frequent regeneration cycles, which in turn increases the energy duty of the unit.

7. Discussion and outlook

This study compares two solid amine-based adsorbents, Lewatit® VP OC 1065 and Purolite® A110, in a 1kg_{CO₂}/day fixed-bed pilot plant to assess their performance. Initial results indicate that Purolite outperforms Lewatit in terms of both CO₂ productivity and energy duty, with 20% higher productivity and 25% lower energy consumption. If all reactors were filled with Purolite, the maximum capacity of the unit would be 1.75 kg_{CO₂}/day, compared to 1.4 kg_{CO₂}/day with Lewatit. This highlights the advantage of Purolite in achieving higher capture rates at lower energy costs.

The study found that medium cycle times were more favorable for Lewatit, while long cycle times benefited Purolite, yielding higher CO₂ working capacities and lower energy duties. Longer cycle times than those examined in this study could potentially provide additional benefits for Purolite. Further research is necessary to validate this hypothesis and explore the implications of extended cycle times on the overall performance. This would help in optimizing operational parameters to maximize CO₂ capture while minimizing energy consumption.

Increased relative humidity of the inlet air enhanced CO₂ working capacity, with a stronger effect observed in Purolite than Lewatit. Previous findings [12] suggest that using purge gas may be cost-effective only at relative humidities below 30%. Given the positive impact of humidity on CO₂ working capacity, it may be more efficient under dry conditions to increase inlet air humidity by injecting water during adsorption, rather than using purge steam during desorption. This approach could enhance the CO₂ adsorption capacity, simplify system infrastructure and improve capacity without the need for steam production.

Sorbent degradation is a crucial factor influencing the economics of the DAC process. In this study, a significant degradation of approximately 55% was observed in the sorbents after around 2000 hours of operation. To better understand this degradation, measuring the oxygen content inside the reactors and identifying the location of the leakages in the reactor could provide valuable insights. This analysis might help identify specific degradation pathways and lead to strategies for enhancing the longevity and performance of the sorbents in DAC applications.

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Appendix A.

A.1. Reproducibility of reactor profiles

(a) CO₂ breakthrough curves

(b) Vacuum pressure of reactor during desorption

Fig A.1.1 Reproducibility of CO₂ breakthrough curves and vacuum pressures.

Fig A.1.2 Reactor bed temperature after cooling sequence of each cycle.

A.2. Comparing parameters

Table A.2.1 Time distribution for the three cycle times used in this study

Sequence time	Short cycle (s)	Medium cycle (s)	Long cycle (s)
Adsorption	6420	9120	11820
Evacuation	60	60	60
Heating	600	600	600
Desorption	900	1800	2700
Cooling	540	540	540
Total	8520	12120	15720
Cycles/day	10.14	7.13	5.50

Fig A.2.2 Variation of CO₂ working capacity of Lewatit and Purolite and Relative humidity for different cycles

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